

EFFECT OF SECONDARY HEAT TREATMENTS ON THE SUPERPLASTICITY OF SiC_p/Zn-22wt.%Al METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES

Greg Heness and Wing Yeung

*Department of Chemistry, Materials and Forensic Science,
University of Technology, Sydney, PO Box 123, Broadway, NSW, 2007, Australia*

SUMMARY: Tensile tests were conducted on SiC_p/Zn-22wt.%Al metal matrix composites. The effect of post warm-rolling heat treatment was investigated. It was found that the heat treatment used reduced the superplasticity of the composites and increased the peak flow stress of the composites. Of interest is the fact that the heat treated composites showed higher strengths than the parent alloy where as the non-heat treated composites were weaker than the parent alloy. A mechanism to account for the observed differences is proposed.

KEYWORDS: Superplasticity, MMC, metal matrix composites, heat treatment

INTRODUCTION

Superplasticity has been a subject of scientific and industrial interest for many years. Since the phenomenon of superplasticity was recognised [1], there have been considerable developments in superplastic alloys. Zn-22 wt.% Al eutectoid alloy was among the first with commercial applications in the manufacture of automotive and engineering components [2, 3]. It has been reported [4-6] that under proper heat treatments, the Zn-22wt.% Al alloy transforms to a fine-grained two-phase equiaxed structure which exhibits optimum superplastic properties at approximately 250°C. Despite superplastic properties exhibited at elevated temperatures, the alloy generally shows rather poor conventional mechanical properties. Alloying additions including copper, silver, silicon, iron, manganese, nickel and lithium have therefore been made in attempts to enhance the mechanical properties. With an optimum control of thermomechanical treatments, some mechanical properties of the alloy have been reported to improve without significantly impairing its superplastic properties [7, 8].

The present study employs a different approach of reinforcing the Zn-22 wt.% Al alloy with SiC particulates. In recent years, development of aluminium and zinc alloy matrix composites has attracted significant industrial interest by virtue of their enhanced mechanical strength and relatively low manufacturing costs [9, 10]. In spite of their higher strengths, the MMCs show poor ductility, restricting their applications in industry. Reinforcement of a superplastic alloy matrix therefore creates a new scope in the development of advanced metal matrix composite materials. A study of SiC whisker reinforced Zn-22 wt.% Al [11] suggested the ductility of the composites was high enough for hot forming of the fabricated products. In the present

study, reinforcement of the alloy with SiC particulates has been attempted to achieve higher strengths whilst maintaining higher deformation ductility. A constant mass fraction of 10% of SiC particulates was added to the Zn-22 wt.% Al alloy and the deformation behaviour and fracture mechanisms of the composites at 250°C were investigated.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Ten mm thick die cast ingots of Zn-22 wt.% Al containing 5, 10, and 40 μm SiC particulates were heat treated and warm rolled under scheduled thermomechanical treatments. The cast ingots were first homogenised at 350°C for 8 hours, quenched in ice water and subsequently heat treated at 250°C for 2 hours before warm rolling. Rolling was carried out at 250°C, deforming the ingots from 10 mm to a final thickness of 1.00-0.80 mm (90-92% C.R.) through nine passes. Secondary heat treatments were applied to the rolled metal aiming to retain an equiaxed fine-grained superplastic structure for the Zn-Al metal matrix. The secondary heat treatments were applied at 350°C for 2 hours, quenched in ice water and then stabilised at 250°C for 1 hour. Tensile pieces of gauge section of 10 (l) x 5 (w) x 1.00-0.80 (t) mm were then prepared from the as-rolled material (NHT) and heat treated material (HT) respectively. Tensile tests of the composites were conducted at 250°C at different initial strain rates ranging from $5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ sec}^{-1}$ to $1 \times 10^{-1} \text{ sec}^{-1}$. Fracture characteristics of the tensile samples were studied by scanning electron microscopy.

RESULTS

Microstructure

The as-cast materials exhibited a cored structure consisting of the α and β phases in the composites (Fig. 1(a)). As expected slow cooling from above the eutectoid temperature (275°C) produces the typical eutectoid lamellar structure. Fast cooling produces a fine grained equiaxed structure (similar to structure observed in Fig 1(c)). Heat treatment and warm rolling at 250°C refined the microstructure. Elongated grains aligned in the rolling direction are observed with plastic flow of the material evident around the particulates (Fig. 1(b)). With the post-rolling heat treatment, an equiaxed fine grained structure developed in the material (Fig. 1(c)). The same microstructural effects were observed in the plain alloy as well.

Fig.1: Typical microstructure of composites (a) as-cast MMC (b) warm-rolled MMC and (c) secondary heat treated MMC.

Effect of Particle Presence

Figs. 2 and 3 show the effect of particle additions on both as-rolled (non-heat treated, NHT) and the heat treated (HT) materials respectively. It can clearly be seen that in both cases the addition of the particles decreases the ductility of the alloy but the ductility decrease is less in the NHT materials. For MMCs, void formation and coalescence are generally observed as the major fracture mechanisms [12]. In a recent study of SiC particulate reinforced Zn-Al composites by the authors [13], void formation and coalescence were observed to develop around the SiC particulates. The particle presence hinders this fracture mechanism via constraint caused by the particles and thus reduces ductility.

Fig. 2: Effect of particle addition on (a) percent elongation and (b) peak flow stress for non-heat treated material.

In the same figures the effect of particle presence on peak flow stress can be observed. For the HT composites the peak flow stress has increased over that of the plain alloy as might be expected. However for the NHT composites decreases in peak flow stress were observed.

Fig. 3: Effect of particle addition on (a) percent elongation and (b) peak flow stress for heat treated material.

Effect of Reinforcement Particle Size

As the inter-particle spacing decreases, either through an increase in reinforcement content or a decrease in particle size, the amount of matrix ligaments for void growth decreases [14-16]. This results in a decrease in ductility of the composites. Figure 4 shows the effect of particle size on the percent elongation of the composite materials. For the heat treated composites (HT) it appears the particle size has little effect on percent elongation at the two lower strain rates. But for the non-heat treated materials (NHT) an increase in ductility is observed with increasing particle size at strain rates of 0.005 and 0.01s⁻¹. At the higher strain rate of 0.05s⁻¹ the percent elongation for the HT material reduces with particle size. For the NHT material the percent elongation remains constant as particle size increases. It can also be seen that for the heat treated condition strain rate appears to have little effect on percent elongation but for the as-rolled composites an increase in strain rate results in a decrease in percent elongation.

Fig. 5 shows the effect of particle size on the peak flow stress for the three strain rates studied in this investigation. For all strain rates the peak flow stress for the plain alloy is higher in the as-rolled (NHT) condition. However, with the addition of particles the heat treated samples show a continuous increase in strength with particle size. For the non-heat treated materials addition of particles reduces peak flow stress initially until a critical particle size where there is a slight increase in stress. There appears, then, to be a critical particle size for the NHT materials above which a strengthening occurs in the material.

Inspection of the graphs in this figure show that as the strain rate is increased the curves for the NHT and HT composites raise. That is, peak flow stress for both warm rolling and heat treatment conditions increase with strain rate.

Fig 4: Effect of particle size on percent elongation at 250 °C for (a) 0.005 sec⁻¹ strain rate, (b) 0.01 sec⁻¹ strain rate and (c) 0.05 sec⁻¹ strain rate [-♦- non-heat treated, -■- heat treated]

Fig 5: Effect of particle size on peak flow stress at 250 °C for (a) 0.005 sec⁻¹ strain rate, (b) 0.01 sec⁻¹ strain rate and (c) 0.05 sec⁻¹ strain rate [-♦- non-heat treated, -■- heat treated]

DISCUSSION

Percent Elongation

In superplastic materials without particulate reinforcement, an equiaxed, fine grained structure forms the basis required for superplastic deformation. In the present study, two different forms of grain structures are established. In the non-heat treated materials, as dynamic recrystallisation occurs in the warm rolling process, an elongated grain structure consisting of fine sized subgrains develops in the materials (Fig. 6(b)). On the other hand, with the post-rolling heat treatment, a structural change occurs and an equiaxed, fine grained structure develops in the metal matrix (Fig 6(a)). Tensile test results of the materials at 250°C show that for the plain alloy, the as-rolled (NHT) materials contain superior percent elongation to the heat treated (HT) materials.

For superplastic materials grain boundary sliding (GBS) is commonly proposed as the main microscopic mechanism responsible for superplasticity [17-21]. As grain boundary sliding becomes the dominant deformation mechanism, the resistance to deformation of the material will be significantly reduced and the flow stress drops. It appears that GBS may have been enhanced by the flow of grains created by warm rolling of the composite material.

Fig. 6. Microstructure for the (a) HT and (b) NHT or as-rolled alloys

The rolled (NHT) composites would also possess a larger residual strain than the HT material. A number of studies have shown that grain boundary misorientation increases with strain [22, 23]. It may be expected that the NHT material would contain a larger number of high angle grain boundaries. The existence of a larger number of high angle grain boundaries is conducive for superplasticity and assists in grain boundary sliding [24]. The authors are currently undertaking textural studies to compare grain boundary angle mismatch in the HT and NHT specimens.

Further, intergranular particles will act as barriers to grain boundary sliding [24], similar to other obstacles such as ledges and triple grain boundary junctions. Thus the general effect of a lowering of the percent elongation and increases in peak flow stresses when particles are added. The observation that the NHT composites exhibited a higher percent elongation than the HT composites may be due to, in addition to the grain boundary angle argument, the flowed grains around the particles (Fig. 1(b)). This natural flow of grains and their grain boundaries may be more conducive to grain boundary sliding than the small equiaxed grains shown in Fig 1(c). The elongated grains may also have a similar effect to that of the sliding of

grain groups mentioned by Malek [25]. Indeed, this argument of grain morphology could be extended to the alloy which shows the same trends in ductility (Fig. 6). For the NHT alloy, high angle grain boundaries aligned parallel to the tensile direction would aid grain boundary sliding.

Inspection of the figures shows that the smaller the particle size, volume fraction kept constant, the less ductile the composites. This is associated with the amount of the matrix ligaments for void growth which in turn affects ductility. For the NHT composites an increase in strain rate reduces the difference in percent elongation. In general this is associated with increase in strength as well. This trend is not clearly represented here. Indeed, both trends seem to be strain rate dependent. For the as rolled composites there is little dependence on particle size shown. However, for the heat treated composites the trend observed is as above and expected.

Peak Flow Stress

The peak flow stress behaviour on addition of the particles is, however, quite different for the two heat treatment conditions (Figs. 2(b) and 3(b)). The heat treated material increases in peak flow stress with the addition of particles. The presence of stiff particles enhances strength. Major strengthening mechanisms in MMCs are (i) the punching of prismatic dislocation loops and the resulting residual stress field due to thermal expansion mismatch strain and (ii) the back stress due to constraint imposed by the stiff reinforcement [26]. Clearly the presence of particles will hinder dislocation movement and thus cause strength increases and ductility decreases. This effect is observed for the HT materials.

In these superplastic composite materials, grain boundary sliding and capable strain accommodation around the particles would promote the superplasticity of the composites and lead to higher percent elongations. Raj [27] has suggested that the presence of the particles, creating a high flow stress that meets the demand of a critical stress criterion for the nucleation of supercritical sliding events.

On the other hand, dislocation movement in the grain interior makes a major contribution to the strength of the materials. Residual stress and back stress built up due to strain mismatch between the metal matrix and the particles hinders dislocation movement and promotes a strengthening mechanism. Pérez-Prado et al. [28] discuss the relative contributions of grain boundary sliding and crystallographic slip in some detail. It is possible that the post-rolling heat treatment may have changed the predominant superplasticity mechanism to crystallographic slip. The authors are currently investigating this.

For the NHT material the particles have a weakening effect. Kim et al. [29] found a similar effect when investigating the superplastic behaviour of SiC particle reinforced 6061 aluminium. In their study they determined that in the temperature range where grain boundary sliding controlled plastic flow, the strength of the composite was lower than the unreinforced matrix alloy even after compensating for grain size and threshold stress. Goto and McClean [30] found that damage accumulation around the reinforcements expected to occur during plastic deformation could reduce the expected strengthening effect of the particles. Cavitation studies on an aluminium MMC supports this argument [31]

Particle Size Effect on Peak Flow Stress

Of interest also is the fact that as the particle size increases so does the peak flow stress for the HT composites but the NHT composites initially decreases and then slowly increases. This is contrary to non-superplastic MMCs, where the increase in particle size allows for a larger mean free path between particles and thus a decrease in strength. The mechanism in these superplastic composites is obviously complicated by the presence of not only dislocation motion but also grain boundary sliding. Larger particles would require more accommodation for grain boundary slip to occur around them.

The higher peak flow stress for the NHT plain alloy (Fig 5) may be explained by the fact that even at the warm rolling condition experienced in this study, some plastic deformation would be present, as evidenced in Figs. 1(b) and 6(b). Recrystallisation on heat treatment would be expected to lower the peak flow stress. Small particles, 5 μm and less, appear to have little effect on this. However as the particle size increases, the HT composites possess a higher peak stress than the NHT composites (Fig (5)). For all strain rates there appears to be a “critical particle size” where this crossover occurs, approximately 7 μm . Then, the HT composites show a higher flow stress than the NHT composite. The effect is even more significant at a strain rate of 0.05 s^{-1} , suggesting that the elongated grain structure in the NHT composites is of a higher strain rate sensitivity and more capable to accommodate plastic deformation during the tensile tests.

The results reflect the complexity of the deformation mechanisms involved in the particulate reinforced Zn-Al composites. In these composite materials, various deformation mechanisms would occur. These include dislocation movement in the grain interior, grain boundary sliding in the metal matrix, and strain accommodation in material around the particles. Another mechanism, proposed by Astanin et al. [32], may be appropriate here, but has not been investigated by the authors at the time of writing. Astanin et al. proposed co-operative grain boundary sliding, a deformation mechanism that does not depend on lattice type and the dislocations present. It depends on the long-range area and structure of grain boundaries.

CONCLUSIONS

Results of the present study show that the grain structure of the metal matrix developed under the different process conditions play a role affecting the operation of various deformation activities. Microscopic examination of the test materials confirms that more compatible strain accommodation had developed between the metal matrix and the reinforced SiC particulates in the warm rolled materials. Elongated grains are observed to align in the rolling direction with plastic flow of the material around the particles. Alignment of the grain boundaries will also limit the interspace for dislocation movement but promote grain boundary sliding along the sample direction in the subsequent superplastic deformation. As a result, high % elongations achieve for the NHT materials. For MMCs with the secondary heat treatments, the SiC particulates are embedded in an equiaxed grain structure. In this structure, strain accommodation of the metal matrix around the reinforced particulates becomes more difficult, and separation between the matrix material and the particles and void formation are ready to occur, resulting in the lower % elongations as observed. Nevertheless, the equiaxed grains will promote dislocation movement inside the grain interior and thus establish a higher strength for the material. The secondary heat treatments applied to the warm rolled materials have thence modified the grain structure of the metal matrix and provided an improved strength over the unreinforced plain alloy. A maximum % elongation of >100% was achieved in the heat treated MMCs.

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